

COLLABORATIVE TECHNIQUES IN DEVELOPING READING SKILLS AMONG GRADE 3 LEARNERS

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Collaborative Techniques in Developing Reading Skills among Grade 3 Learners

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Abstract

The aim of the study was to determine the effectiveness of Collaborative Techniques in improving the reading skills of Grade 3 learners in Bitoon Elementary School for the Academic year 2022-2023 as basis for development of reading design program. This study utilized single group quasi-experimental pretest-posttest using the EGRA scores were taken both before and after the Collaborative techniques. The design also employed t-test of dependence to determine if there a significant difference between reading skills and type of readers in Grade 3 pupils before and after the Collaborative reading techniques had been employed. The findings of the study revealed that there are improvements in the reading skills of the pupils across all categories of reading skills whereby Oral Reading Comprehension 1 and 2 have an average improvement while Listening Comprehension, Invented Word Recording, Oral Reading Fluency Passage 1 and 2 and Dictation have excellent improvement. There was a significant improvement in the Levels of Learners' Reading Skills across all skills categories between the Pretest and Post-test scores. This shows that there was sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. This highlights that the intervention which is the Collaborative Technique extend efficacy on the learner's level of reading skills. The results coincide wherein reading skills in the pretest and posttest have been significant. The mean gain in the posttest from the pretest scores of the Learners' Reading Skills across the categories of reading skills are significant. Therefore, there is sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis based on the results of the study. This shows Collaborative reading technique was an effective strategy to develop the reading skills of the learners.

Keywords: *collaborative reading techniques, reading status, reading skills, pretest, post test*

Introduction

Although literacy emphasizes those who work, it may boost a person's standards of life (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), 2008). There is a clear correlation between literacy and academic success. Hence, training individuals with good literacy who can comprehend and question what they read is one of the most important goals for today's education (Moreillan, 2007). It is in a similar idea stating that success in school depends on a large part of the child's ability to read. Thus, when children become good readers in their early grades, they are more likely to become better learners throughout the school years and beyond.

Eighty percent of the Filipino students did not reach the minimum level of proficiency in reading. The reasons behind this, non-mastery of the elements of reading, presence of learners-at-risk, and no culture of reading (Tomas et al., 2021). In the Philippines, regulations were set to foster the idea that reading is an important skill for children to learn. In this connection, the Department of Education in the National Capital Region (NCR) established a memorandum order number 67, series of 2014 otherwise known as The No Read, No Pass Policy. Learning to read and understand what is being read entails hard work for children as well as to educators. Educators aim at producing children who are readers because learning lies mainly in the child's ability to read and comprehend. However, such goal is a shared concern by pupils, parents, teachers, school officials and every citizen. Making children read and comprehend is a difficult undertaking. It is not enough to have an understanding of reading as only identifying the letters and words and speaking them. Reading with accuracy is an additional skill that needs to be cultivated in reading instruction, in addition to comprehension of written material Isik, Ayse Derya, (2023). According to Claessen et al. As Al. (2020) noted, there are reading difficulties throughout the world. The results of the 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) reveal that reading is one of the subject areas in which fifteen-year-old Filipino pupils performed worse than students in the majority of the participating nations and economies. There are several factors that have been identified that affect the child's ability to read and comprehend. Some of the more widely recognized causes of reading problems are vision and hearing impairments, poor speech, and language development. Other school children have problems with reading because of learning disabilities. Whatever the cause or nature of a child's reading problem, the earlier the difficulty is discover and additional help provided, the better the child's chance of becoming a successful reader. On the bright side, no matter how long it takes, with few exceptions, a child can learn how to read and the problem is how to comprehend what was read.

One of the most important roles parents can play concerning their children's schoolwork is that of a cheerleader. Applauding their efforts and their successes, especially in reading, help them to boost the confidence of the child. Testing how they understand the topic is also another challenge for the parents. Encouraging them to keep trying and supporting them in this endeavor to mold the child to be a good reader and be able to explain the subject he/she reads as they grow older. Parents' involvement and monitoring of their child's progress can help the child become a better reader and for better comprehension. Parent involvement is a critical way for children to learn about the importance of education and develop reading skills. This has a positive impact on children's reading skills, but that impact can be contingent on what occurs within the classroom. This study underscores the need to consider both home and school influences on children's reading skills (Gay et al., 2021).

As I talked with my co-teachers handling grade three, most of their pupils find it hard in reading. For this reason, this study is conducted to determine how effective collaborative techniques can be of use in teaching reading to grade three learners. Furthermore, the study aims to supplement quantitative data in order to provide a description and characterization of reading teachers' reading development approaches. The data will extrapolate implications that will serve as a guide for developing a reading program.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the effectiveness of Collaborative Techniques in improving the reading skills of Grade 3 learners in Bitoon Elementary School for the Academic year 2022-2023 as basis for development of reading design program. The study specifically aimed to respond to the following:

1. What are the levels of learners' reading skills in the Pretest and Post-test as to:
 - 1.1. Listening Comprehension (LC);
 - 1.2. Invented Word Decoding (IWD);
 - 1.3. Oral Reading Fluency Passage 1 (ORFP1);
 - 1.4. Oral Reading Comprehension 1 (ORC1);
 - 1.5. Oral Reading Fluency 2 (ORF2);
 - 1.6. Oral Reading Comprehension 2 (ORC2); and
 - 1.7. Dictation (D)?
2. Is there significant difference between the levels of learners' reading skills in the pretest and post-test?
3. Is there a significant mean gain in the post-test from the pretest scores of the learners' reading skills?
4. Based on the results of the study, what personalized reading program can be developed?

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized single group quasi-experimental pretest-posttest design is a type of non-randomized research approach used to evaluate intervention or treatment where there is no control group. This type of research design measures the outcomes of before and after an intervention was conducted. In this study, the intervention was a Collaborative technique on Grade 3 pupils of Bitoon Elementary School for the Academic Year 2022-23. In this design, EGRA scores were taken both before and after the Collaborative techniques were administered by the researcher. The design also employed t-test of dependence to determine if there was a significant difference between reading skills and type of readers in Grade 3 pupils before and after the Collaborative reading techniques had been employed. Other alternative designs were not applied because the purpose of the study is to know the significant difference of before and after the intervention done.

Participants

The participants of the study were all Grade 3 learners comprising of two sections at Bitoon Elementary School for the School Year 2022-2023. One section was composed of 31 pupils and another section composed of 25 pupils with a total of 56 pupils in the sample size. They were residents of Bitoon, Daanbantayan Cebu. The source of living of their families was mainly fishing and farming.

The study was conducted in Bitoon Elementary School in Daanbantayan Cebu where the learners from the locality took up kindergarten, primary and intermediate classes. There were two sections for Grade 3 classes. The learning institution existed for more than 70 years. Its main thrust is to provide quality education to the children of the locality. The school is well supervised by the Department of Education under the supervision of the Division Superintendent and School District Supervisor. There were 18 teachers and 1 principal. Thirteen (13) of the teachers are teaching English. The total population of learners for AY 2022-2023 was 555.

Instruments

The main instrument used was the Early Grade Reading Assessment (EGRA). This was taken from the Department of Education (DepEd Memorandum No. 24, s. 2013 and DepEd Order No. 57, s. 2015). EGRA is an assessment tool that measures the level of reading skills in early grades. It is designed to diagnose the pupils' progress toward learning to read and thus enable class teachers, school administrators and parents, to monitor their learning. The primary skills assessed in the EGRA are:

Table 1. *Primary skills assessed in EGRA*

<i>Sub-task</i>	<i>What is Assessed</i>
Listening Comprehension	ability to listen and understand a passage being read
Invented Word Decoding	ability to apply knowledge of letter sound relationship
Oral Reading Fluency	Ability on how quickly, accurately, automatically and expressively someone reads.
Oral Reading Comprehension	ability to quickly and accurately read connected text on a page and answer comprehension questions about what has been read
Dictation	ability to accurately transcribes speech to text in real time

Procedure

Pre-data Collection. Once the conduct of the survey was approved by the Dean of the University of the Visayas. The researcher made a communication letter to the principal and superintendent of the concerned school for approval to conduct the study to grade 3 learners at Bitoon Elementary School for the School Year 2022-2023. Then, a parent's consent was deployed to grade 3 pupils for their approval of the conduct of the study. Upon the return and collection of consent, the researcher ensured that all consent was signed and verified the authenticity of the parents' signatures. Afterward, the researcher asked permission to the grade 3 pupils and conduct the orientation on the purpose of the study, aims, and benefits. Then, the survey questionnaire was prepared by the researcher and was conducted during the respondents' English class time. Also, the classroom materials were prepared and used during the actual class activities anchored on Collaborative technique. Once everything was set, the researcher proceeded to the actual conduct of the study.

Data Collection Phase. The researcher explained the instructions prior to the implementation of the Collaborative technique in the class. The researcher deployed the research instrument to be answered by the Grade 3 pupils for the pretest. Ample time was given to the Grade 3 pupils. After the duration of the study, the research instrument was again conducted for the post-test. The results of the survey questionnaires was kept with the utmost confidentiality and follow the privacy act section 16 the rights of the data subject and section 20 the security of personal information.

After the data was gathered, the results were treated with statistical tools and were interpreted and analyzed to answer the research problems. The summary of results was constructed and came up with the conclusions and recommendations of the study. Based on the recommendations, an output was realized.

Post -Data Collection Phase. After the survey questionnaires conducted, the researcher collected the data from the respondents. The statistical tools was conceptualized for interpretation and analysis of the data gathered. Then all the utilized data were stored and kept in a safety place for security purposes and for future references.

Data Analysis

The data gathered, analyzed and interpreted using an identified statistical tool. A Frequency and Percentage was used to determine the frequency of reader and non-reader for the reading skills using the Early Grade Reading Assessment Tool (EGRA), t-test for dependence to know whether there are significance difference in the reading skills between pretest and posttest, and t-test for single group to determine and check the significant difference in the mean gains of pretest and posttest using EGRA.

For the level of learners' reading skills in the Pretest and Post-test. The following parameters were used.

<i>Reading Skills</i>	<i>Excellent</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Needs Improvement</i>
Listening Comprehension	2.34-3.00	1.67-2.33	1.00-1.66
Invented Word Decoding	33.67-50.00	17.33-33.66	1.00-17.32
Oral Reading Fluency Passage 1	39.67-59.00	20.33-39.66	1.00-20.32
Oral Reading Comprehension1 & 2	3.67-5.00	2.33-3.66	1.00-2.32
Oral Reading Fluency Passage 2: Decoding	40.34-60.00	20.66-40.33	1.00-20.65
	20.34-30	10.66-20.33	1.00-10.65
For Overall	141.65-212	71.32-141.64	1.00-71.32

Ethical Considerations

Everyone has the right to privacy and confidentiality of personal information. Dealing with this the researcher send a parental consent letter to the parents of the concerned student respondents. Taking into consideration that some of the respondents are minors, it is indicated in the letter that participation is voluntary and further guidance and orientation is done to the minors once the parents agreed and have affixed their signatures. Rest assured that data shall be kept in secrecy. To uphold the ethical practices of research and to avoid breaching the human rights of the respondents and other people that would contribute to the accomplishment of the research work the following ethical measures are considered.

Risk and Benefits

The research study was a quantitative using survey questionnaires to assess students' level in reading comprehension and their academic performance. It was understood that the IRB cannot approve studies that post potential risk to the respondents, questionnaires that endangers their personal dignity and privacy.

However the study was perceived by the researcher posts no significant and potential risk to the respondent groups as there was no data mining needed, Questions reflected in the survey questionnaires possess no potential risk of inflicting psychological trauma to the respondents, thus the study benefited the respondents hence the output of the study served as their guide in choosing a career path which would be the life time basis of their vocation and means of livelihood.

It is just emphasized that their participation is voluntary, parental consent and assent are secured before floating the questionnaires and

orientation is done before actual survey questionnaires are distributed. Data obtained are kept in total privacy and the questionnaires are burned right after the tally.

Content, Comprehension and Documentation of Informed consent.

To protect the privacy of the respondents, a written consent form with an IRB approval letter was sent to them along a notice on the study's purpose. The respondent's signature on the consent form certifies that they have agreed to the conditions attached to the research, and participation in the study is completely voluntary.

The following are the provisions provided in the consent form:

Participant status. Respondents had understood clearly that the study is only about getting their demographic profile and their scores in reading test with their grades in the previous grade in English subject and there is no data mining needed.

Study Goals. The researcher presented to the respondents the purpose of the study before floating the questionnaires. A thorough orientation is conducted to ascertain that the respondents are totally aware of the goals of the study including its potential beneficiaries.

Type of data. Prior to the conduct of the questionnaire, they were oriented on the type of data that they will be asked for, data were previous general average in English and their scores in reading test.

Procedures. Data collection procedure only involves distribution of survey questionnaires. Results were transcribed and burned after obtaining the data needed and tallied.

Nature of the Commitment. The researcher made use of the student's vacant time with the adviser's consent. The survey will only take 1 hour which includes the orientation of the survey and the survey parts.

Sponsorship. The study was part of an academic requirement and the expenses incurred are financed by the researcher.

Participant selection. The study chose the grade 3 pupils of Bitoon Elementary School to be the respondents of the study thus they will be the recipient of the output of the study.

Potential Risks. The researcher identified minor risk especially in the conduct of the study because they will be asked to render about 1 hour in answering. The researcher tried her best to keep the respondents in their most relax moments to avoid stress both physically and emotionally.

Potential Benefits. Identified potential benefits to the respondents are that they will be the recipient of enhancement reading program that would guide help them and enhance their skill in reading since this is very useful as they move to the next grades.

Alternatives. The study simply employed survey questionnaires that could be done and accomplished for minimum period of time thus alternatives is not considered by the researcher.

Compensation. There was no compensation given to the respondents only simple token of appreciation.

Confidentiality pledge. To protect the privacy of the respondents, anonymity was guaranteed by not mentioning their names in the manuscript, only codes were used.

Voluntary consent. The participation of respondents was all voluntary and no amount of coercion was applied. Any private information was only disclosed to the researcher.

Right to withdraw and withhold information. Respondents were informed that they can withheld information if they wish to and withdraw from participation if they like to anytime.

Contact Information. The researcher provided the respondents with her contact number and University of the Visayas contact number if ever they have questions, comments or complains regarding the conduct of the study especially on the gathering of data. They can contact the IRB office Address: UV Main Colon St. Cebu City Email: uvirb2015@gmail.com Tel: 416-8607 Mobile: 0943-533049

Authorization to access private information was included in the consent form and private information was disclosed only to the researcher. In totality, there is no private information that could endanger the respondents dignity foreseen in the study however every data taken withheld with utmost anonymity and confidentiality.

Confidentiality Procedure. The study utilizes survey questionnaires related to their profiles along with their previous general average in English and their scores in reading comprehension test thus there is no potential factor that would endanger respondent's dignity yet for securing the utmost confidentiality of the respondents, they were not asked to reflect their names on the questionnaire and after the interpretation of data, the questionnaires shall be turned over to UV-IRB office for safe keeping.

Debriefing, communications and referrals. Since the study utilizes only survey questionnaires and test on matters only pertinent to courses of preference, the researcher found nothing in the research that is potential of inflicting psychological trauma to respondents thus debriefing is found to be not necessary after the conduct of the study.

Incentives or compensation. The time and effort asked from the respondents is very minimal added that it is done during their free time much more that the number of respondents is too high. They were not given any compensation or honoraria considering that the study is funded from the personal pockets of the researcher. Anyway, after the conduct of the study, heartfelt and profound gratitude were uttered and extended by the researcher for the students' participation towards the completion of this humble work.

Conflict of interest. The conduct of the study was smooth sailing thus there was no slightest signs manifested that there is a conflict of interest thus managing conflict of interest is not applicable in this study.

Vulnerability Assessment. The researcher identified no potential risk that might inflict minors of the data accounted for. Data gathered are all positive and friendly to human dignity including to minors. There is no other step to be undertaken except securing parental consent, debriefing and further orientation and assuring the confidentiality and secrecy of the data. This no data mining needed as all responses shall be rated through given indicators alone.

Results and Discussion

This section shows the presentation, analyses, and interpretation of the data gathered to answer the problems of the study.

The Level of Reading Skills of Grade 3 Pupils in English

Table 2. Below is the table of Frequency of Reader & Non-Reader in the Pretest Reading Skills of Grade 3 Learners

Sections	Modest (N=31)		Adorable (N=25)		Overall (N=56)			
	R	NR	R	NR	R	%	NR	%
Skills								
LC	2	29	7	18	9	16.07%	47	83.93%
IWR	2	29	7	18	9	16.07%	47	83.93%
ORFP1	2	29	7	18	9	16.07%	47	83.93%
ORC1	1	30	6	19	7	12.50%	49	87.50%
ORFP2	1	30	6	19	7	12.50%	49	87.50%
ORC2	1	30	4	21	5	8.93%	51	91.07%
D	2	29	0	25	2	3.57%	54	96.43%
Overall	2	29	7	18	9	16.07%	47	83.93%

Based on Table 2 in the listening comprehension, 16.07% of the Grade 3 learners have a reader status during the pretest while 83.93% of them have non-reader status. The least skill among learners with reader status in the pretest is Dictation (D). While the top skills in the pretest among the reader learners are Listening Comprehension (LC), Invented Word Decoding (IWD), and Oral Reading Fluency Passage 1 (ORFP1). Learners with non-reader status in the pretest have most difficulty at dictation (D), followed by Oral Reading Comprehension 2 (ORC2). This merely signifies that many of the Grade 3 pupils reading status based on the above sub skills shows inadequately developed due to self-learning modules utilized during pandemic where less instructional contact and practices with the teacher. In study conducted by Ulrech et al (2022) on fourth graders' reading achievement based on a school panel study, utilizing the Progress in International Reading Literacy Study instruments in 2016 and 2021. The results showed a substantial decline in reading achievement was related to the COVID-19 pandemic that pupils had to self-regulate their learning at home. Likewise, Tomas, M. Villaros, E. and Galman, S. (2021) investigated the perceived challenges in reading of learners as basis for school reading program. It showed that the majority of the learners were inadequately developed. A total 4056 Filipino reading profiles and 4216 English reading profiles of Grade 1 to Grade 7 students and responses from the interviews done with school heads and teachers were described using descriptive measures and analyzed using thematic analysis.

Below is the table of the Frequency of Reader and Non-Reader in the Posttest Reading Skills of Grade 3 Learners.

Table 3. The frequency of reader and non- reader Grade 3 learners in English in their posttest

Sections	Modest (N=31)		Adorable (N=25)		Overall (N=56)			
	R	NR	R	NR	R	%	NR	%
Skills								
LC	4	27	13	12	17	30.36%	39	69.64%
IWR	4	27	13	12	17	30.36%	39	69.64%
ORFP1	4	27	12	13	16	28.57%	40	71.43%
ORC1	3	28	10	15	13	23.21%	43	76.79%
ORFP2	3	28	13	12	16	28.57%	40	71.43%
ORC2	3	28	12	13	15	26.79%	41	73.21%
D	4	27	7	18	11	19.64%	45	80.36%
Overall	4	27	10	15	14	25.00%	42	75.00%

As shown in Table 3 in the listening comprehension, the Grade 3 pupils who have achieved reader status after posttest is 30.36%. Meanwhile, 69.64% of them still have a non-reader status. The least skill among pupils with reader status in the posttest is the Dictation (D). While the top skills in the posttest among the reader pupils are Listening Comprehension (LC) and Invented Word Decoding (IWD).

(IWD). Learners with non-reader status in the pretest had difficulty at Dictation (D), followed by Oral Reading Comprehension (1).

Based on the results of the reading sub skills of the learners, a substantial number were identified as non-readers in spite of utilizing the intervention on collaborative techniques. This result might be due to the fact that these learners were products of distance learning in the previous grades where meaningful interaction with the teacher were very limited. In any event in the study Mataac (2022), he found that Modular Distance Learning affects the reading development of pupils. One factor is that some parents were not trained to teach reading and some of them are non-readers. Though teachers did their visitation to the learners at their home for assistance and scaffolding whenever possible, but still the time is limited and may not be able to visit all their pupils in their time of availability. There are para-teachers and teacher volunteers serve as aid however with the guidelines and protocols mandated by IATF, home visitations are controlled. In addition, the study PHIL-IRI given the data imply that mediation between pretest and posttest as per DepEd Order No. 45 s, 2002 otherwise known as Reading Literacy Program in the Elementary School where the policy “Every Child A Reader”, has slightly taking effect until COVID-19 came to picture. However, previous study revealed that despite several flagship programs and reading intervention and innovative reading strategies being implemented, still the result of PHIL-IRI on frustration is still prevalent.

Below is the results of the learner reading skills in the Pretest and Posttest.

Table 4. *The level of learners’ reading skills in the Pretest and Post-test.*

Skills	Pretest			Post-Test		
	\bar{x}	SD	Description	\bar{x}	SD	Description
Listening Comprehension	1.89	0.98	Average	2.73	0.77	Excellent
Invented Word Recording	16.32	17.12	Needs Improvement	37.89	13.57	Excellent
Oral Reading Fluency Passage 1	16.95	18.08	Needs Improvement	40.07	14.63	Excellent
Oral Reading Comprehension 1	1.73	1.21	Needs Improvement	3.61	1.12	Average
Oral Reading Fluency Passage 2	17.39	18.36	Needs Improvement	42.57	14.19	Excellent
Oral Reading Comprehension 2	2.05	1.27	Needs Improvement	3.46	1.17	Average
Dictation	8.04	8.16	Needs Improvement	20.79	7.99	Excellent
Overall	64.38	60.59	Needs Improvement	151.13	50.14	Excellent

n=56 LC: Needs Improvement-1.00-1.66; Average-1.67-2.33; Excellent-2.34-3.00; IWR: Needs Improvement-1.00-17.32; Average-17.33-33.66; Excellent-33.67-50.00; O RFP1: Needs Improvement-1.00-20.32; Average-20.33-39.66; Excellent-39.67-59.00; ORC1 & ORC2: Needs Improvement-1.00-2.32; Average-2.33-3.66; Excellent-3.67-5.00; ORFP2: Needs Improvement-1.00-20.65; Average-20.66-40.33; Excellent-40.34-60.00; D: Needs Improvement-1.00-10.65; Average-10.66-20.33; Excellent-20.34-30; Overall: Needs Improvement-1.00-71.32; Average-71.32-141.64; Excellent-141.65-212

As presented in Table 4, it shows that there are improvements in the reading skills of the pupils across all categories of reading skills whereby Oral Reading Comprehension 1 and 2 have an average improvement while Listening Comprehension, Invented Word Recording, Oral Reading Fluency Passage 1 and 2 and Dictation have Excellent improvement. This proves that the intervention has made some improvement in the reading skills of the learners. As demonstrated by the study carried out in a primary school context, this further demonstrates how intervention programs considerably boost learning achievement and develop positive attitudes toward learning in low achiever learners. According to a study by Shankar Shubba and Hem Kumar Gotamey (2022), low achiever adolescents can become academically successful adults if teachers promote educational equity by implementing intervention programs in the classroom, like collaborative strategies employing EGRA. This result is in line with a study conducted in April 2024 by Helena Vellinho Corso et al., which concentrated on reading comprehension skill intervention. According to the authors, reading comprehension entails a variety of intricate linguistic and cognitive functions, including inference-making, word recognition, and fluency in decoding. Numerous kids and teenagers struggle with this, which has a detrimental impact on their academic achievement and future career prospects. They stress the value of efficient interventions that enhance reading comprehension by putting a focus on inference-making and classroom training. The chapter emphasizes how neuropsychological evaluation helps pinpoint the right interventions and identify particular challenges. Furthermore, they explain that research has demonstrated notable enhancements in reading proficiency following interventions. Interventions pertaining to executive functioning are among them. The school is essential in the context of prevention.

The Significant difference of Learners’ Reading Skills of Grade 3 Learners in Pretest and Posttest

Below presents the results of the t-test between the levels of the learners’ reading skills in the pretest and post-test.

Table 5. *Significant Difference of the Levels of Learners’ Reading Skills between the Pretest and Post-test.*

Skills	p-value	t-value	df	Decision
Listening Comprehension	<.00001*	5.506423	110	Reject H0
Invented Word Recording	<.00001*	8.344348	110	Reject H0
Oral Reading Fluency Passage 1	<.00001*	8.385073	110	Reject H0
Oral Reading Comprehension 1	<.00001*	9.416171	110	Reject H0
Oral Reading Fluency Passage 2	<.00001*	8.847165	110	Reject H0
Oral Reading Comprehension 2	<.00001*	6.534426	110	Reject H0
Dictation	<.00001*	9.316528	110	Reject H0
Overall	<.00001*	8.999979	110	Reject H0

Note. n=56

As displayed in Table 5, there is a significant improvement in the Levels of Learners’ Reading Skills across all skills categories between

the Pretest and Post-test scores. This shows that there is sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. This highlights that the intervention which is the Collaborative Technique extend efficacy on the learner's level of reading skills. This is consistent with a study by Ali Amjadi and Seyed Hassan Talebi (2024), which found that reading skills increased significantly following reading instruction using collaborative methodologies, regardless of the type of intervention and question categories. Even with this potential for modest improvement, collaborative approach is still a useful tactic for teaching reading skills. The study conducted by Rozanah Katrina Herda in December 2023 found that the shift in learning from an online to an offline form in the aftermath of the pandemic has an impact on the reading comprehension of EFL students who are having difficulty. The purpose of this quasi-experimental study, which used a One-Group Pretest-Posttest design, was to ascertain whether there was a significant difference between the mean scores on the reading pretest and posttest obtained through the use of Collaborative Strategic Reading (CSR), as well as to uncover the opinions of the students regarding the use of CSR in the reading classroom. Participants were sixty-eight seniors in an Indonesian high school. A questionnaire and a pretest-posttest were used to gather data. The results of the pretest and posttest showed that employing CSR as a reading method greatly enhanced students' comprehension of collaborative nuance. Positive views were held by the pupils regarding the use of CSR.

Significant Mean Gain in the Posttest from the Pretest Scores of the Learners' Reading Skills

Below is the Significant Difference of the Mean Gain in the Posttest from the Pretest scores of the Learners' Reading Skills.

Table 6. Significant mean gain in the posttest from the pretest scores of the Learners' Reading Skills

Skills	Mean Gain	df	p-value	Findings	Decision
Listening Comprehension	0.84	55	<.00001*	Significant	Reject H0
Invented Word Recording	21.57	55	<.00001*	Significant	Reject H0
Oral Reading Fluency Passage 1	23.13	55	<.00001*	Significant	Reject H0
Oral Reading Comprehension 1	1.88	55	<.00001*	Significant	Reject H0
Oral Reading Fluency Passage 2	25.18	55	<.00001*	Significant	Reject H0
Oral Reading Comprehension 2	1.41	55	<.00001*	Significant	Reject H0
Dictation	12.75	55	<.00001*	Significant	Reject H0
Overall	86.75	55	<.00001*	Significant	Reject H0

n=56

As presented in Table 5, the results coincide with the results in Table 3 and Table 4 where reading skills in the pretest and posttest have been significant. In Table 5, the mean gain in the posttest from the pretest scores of the Learners' Reading Skills across the categories of reading skills are significant. Therefore, there is sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis based on the results of the study. This shows Collaborative reading technique was an effective strategy to develop the reading skills of the learners. It was concluded in the study that the post-test means were significantly higher from the pretest mean. Despite the number of non-reader learners as shown in Table 1 and Table 2, there was still significant progress in the reading skills in terms of the scores. Though, more efforts are needed to improve the number of reader learners. The presentation investigated whether pretest reading skills impacted the efficacy of intervention in struggling adolescent readers, according to a study by Eric L. Oslund et al. published in February 2018. The findings show that fluency in oral reading moderated the effect. According to the Johnson-Neyman, there was a statistically significant positive correlation between the treatment and the effect of the intervention conditioned on pretest oral reading fluency. Approximately 64% of the sample was included in the significant region.

Conclusions

The study concludes that despite significant progress in reading skills, as indicated by the improvement in scores from pretest to posttest, a considerable number of learners remained non-readers. This suggests that while some students have effectively transitioned to becoming readers, a significant portion still struggles with reading. The results affirm that socio-cultural and reading theories, which emphasize meaningful interactions between teachers and learners, alongside active participation in collaborative techniques, play a crucial role in enhancing reading skills. The study highlights the need for more efforts, particularly in addressing challenges post-COVID-19, to further improve reading skills among learners.

The findings suggest that although collaborative techniques and the use of Early Grade Reading Assessment (EGRA) have significantly improved reading skills, the transition from non-reader to reader has not been as widespread as hoped. The contrasting results in the tables indicate that while there are positive developments, there is still much work to be done to address the challenges faced by learners, particularly in the context of the pandemic's aftermath. The study emphasizes the importance of continued efforts to support learners' reading development through targeted strategies and interventions.

Based on the study's findings, several recommendations are proposed. Teachers should innovate and adapt their teaching methods to fit the diverse learning environments and styles of their pupils, focusing on improving reading comprehension and skills. The government should invest in resources and funding for reading initiatives, including providing access to learning tools and online platforms. Schools should foster partnerships with educational organizations and NGOs to implement evidence-based reading programs. Additionally, encouraging family and community involvement in literacy programs is crucial. Future research should explore

other factors affecting reading abilities in flexible learning environments, and the Department of Education should establish clear policies to support pupils' reading improvement.

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